

FACTOR ANALYSIS OF THE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT OF INVESTMENT FUNDS IN UKRAINE**Shmorhun I.***PhD student**Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv***Abstract**

The article carries out a factor analysis of the business environment of investment funds in Ukraine. It is found that investment funds in Ukraine have significant potential for development due to the growing role of digital platforms and the introduction of opportunities to purchase securities through mobile applications or websites, and due to the availability of a small number of market alternatives during martial law. At the same time, their growth is constrained by weaknesses, such as an increase in the number of competitors in the market while reducing the number of suppliers in the form of asset management companies.

Keywords: factor analysis, business environment, investment funds, SWOT analysis, PESTEL analysis, investments.

The business environment of business entities is usually unstable and subject to frequent changes, which in turn requires regular monitoring of market factors and prompt response to relevant changes. This is especially true today, when the world has only recently recovered from the COVID-19 pandemic and its consequences, and now Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine is underway, which has implications for the whole world.

Factor analysis of the business environment of investment funds in Ukraine is an important tool for understanding the key conditions that affect their activities. The formation and development of investment funds depend on the interaction of economic, political, social and technological factors that determine the dynamics of the country's financial market. In the context of Ukraine's transformational economy, these factors have specific features: from the impact of the regulatory environment, which was shaped by European integration processes, to the impact of the war, which changed investment priorities.

Factor analysis of the business environment of a business entity in the modern world can be carried out using various methods. Thus, one of the first and still used analysis tools is PEST analysis. PEST-analysis (Political, Economic, Social, Technological) as a tool for analyzing the external environment was proposed in the middle of the XX century, and its ideas are largely based on the work of Aguillard Fr. He was the first to describe a structured approach to analyzing the environmental factors affecting business [2]. Aguillard used four main categories of factors that formed the basis of PEST analysis, although he did not call this approach PEST. Later, this model was expanded to PESTEL (including Environmental and Legal factors) to meet the modern realities of analysis.

There is also a methodology for studying the factors of the business environment of companies based on the analysis of macro- and micro-marketing environment factors. The key persons who laid the foundations and developed this methodology are:

- Kotler F.: described a detailed approach to the analysis of the marketing environment, including macro (demographic, economic, social, technological, political and cultural factors) and micro factors (consumers, suppliers, competitors, intermediaries) [3];

- Ansoff I.: proposed the concept of strategic analysis, which includes an analysis of the internal and external environment of the organization, laying the foundations for approaches to the study of the business environment [4];

- Porter M.: described in detail the company's micro-environment, including interaction with suppliers, competitors, customers, substitutes and new market players [5].

Additionally, there is also a SWOT analysis method. SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) is a strategic planning method used to assess internal and external factors that affect an organization, project, or business. In 1963, at Harvard University, Professor Andrews K. first introduced a method of systematizing and analyzing information, which was later called SWOT analysis.

Table 1 shows the key advantages and disadvantages of such methods of studying the external and internal environment of investment funds in Ukraine as PESTEL analysis, analysis of marketing environment factors, including factors of micro and macro marketing environment, and SWOT analysis.

Table 1

Advantages and disadvantages of methods of analysis of external and internal environment of investment funds in Ukraine

Methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
PESTEL-analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on macro factors: PESTEL analysis allows to identify the impact of global and national factors on the activities of investment funds: political stability, economic trends, technological innovations, legislative changes, etc; • Particularly relevant for strategic planning: in the context of Ukraine's realities, this method will help to take into account, for example, the impact of war, international sanctions or regulatory policy on the development of collective investment institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This method is less suitable for assessing interaction with specific market participants than the next method.
Analysis of marketing environment factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of micro and macro factors: this approach covers not only global trends, but also specific interactions with key market participants (customers, competitors, suppliers); • Relevance for tactical decisions: this method is relevant for certain tactical decisions, in particular at the micro level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The analysis of macro factors is less in-depth and detailed than the PESTEL analysis.
SWOT-analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Versatility and simplicity: SWOT analysis helps to identify the internal strengths and weaknesses of funds, as well as external opportunities and threats to their operation; • Combined coverage of factors: this approach allows to combine macro- and micro-analysis, which can be useful for developing strategies or assessing the competitiveness of funds. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This method does not provide sufficiently deep detail of external factors that provide a PESTEL analysis or marketing approach.

Source: compiled by the author based on [6-11]

After analyzing the key advantages and disadvantages of methods of researching the external and internal environment of investment funds in Ukraine, such as PESTEL analysis, analysis of marketing environment factors, including factors of micro and macro

marketing environment, and SWOT analysis, the author decided to conduct a factor analysis of the business environment according to the following algorithm (Fig.1).

Fig. 1 Algorithm of factor analysis of the business environment of investment funds in Ukraine

Source: author's development

Table 2 presents a list of groups of macro-environmental factors and the factors corresponding to these groups that affect the activities of investment funds in the Ukrainian market.

Factors of macro-environment of investment funds in the Ukrainian market	
Group of factors	Factors
Political	- russia's full-scale war against Ukraine
	- Deeper integration with the EU
	- Low level of political stability (Political Stability Index)
	- High level of corruption (Corruption Perception Index)
	- Stability of the global economy despite uncertainty
Economical	- Reduction of economic and financial assistance from international partners
	- Growth of the GDP level
	- Increase in the level of taxes
	- Increase in the rate of inflation
	- Devaluation of the national currency
Social	- Changes in investment preferences of the population
	- Decrease in population
	- External and internal emigration against the backdrop of the Russian-Ukrainian war
	- Occupation of a part of Ukraine
	- Low level of financial literacy of the population
Technological	- Low level of human development index
	- Digitalization of financial services
	- Decrease in the share of expenditures on research and development in relation to GDP
	- Development of financial technologies and big data
	- Emergence of regulation in the field of sustainable investment and financing
Environmental	- Negative environmental consequences caused by the war
	- Unification with EU standards
Legal	- Low level of rule of law (WJP Rule of Law Index)
	- Ban on cross-border currency transfers from Ukraine

Source: compiled by the author according to [12-38].

The analysis of macro environment factors begins with the analysis of political factors. The most important elements of this environment are legislation, government groups, global indices and ratings. Political stability and the level of corruption also affect business activity. However, for all business entities in Ukraine, the most important political factor and obviously an obstacle to normal operation is a full-scale war. Below, we will analyze the political factors in more detail:

- russia's full-scale war against Ukraine. This factor is currently the most important for a business entity in almost every field of activity in Ukraine, as war always has negative economic, demographic, environmental, and infrastructure consequences, especially for the country against which the war is waged. This factor significantly hinders the development of Ukrainian investment funds and the Ukrainian stock market, as well as inhibits the attraction of non-resident legal entities and individuals to invest in Ukrainian investment funds;

- deepening integration with the EU. According to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, the EU is one of Ukraine's largest trade and investment partners, and the EU's share in the overall structure of international trade and investment has been increasing in recent years [12]. This fact shows that domestic investment funds are able to work with securities issued by European issuers and European stock indices. However, first of all, Ukraine needs to adapt as soon as possible to the European legislation and regulations concerning the activities of investment funds and the stock market in general;

- Ukraine's political stability index as of 2023 is -1.43 (-1.52 in 2019). According to this indicator, Ukraine ranks 172nd out of 193 countries [13]. Such a

low level of this indicator is mainly caused by the war in Ukraine and should be considered as a threat to Ukrainian investment funds, because due to the unstable political situation in the country, there is a high level of uncertainty, and therefore high risks regarding the activities and possible changes in the regulation of investment funds;

- according to the Corruption Perceptions Index as of 2023, Ukraine ranked 104th out of 180 countries (117th in 2019) with a score of 36/100 points [14]. For foreign investment funds and investors, this factor is seen as a threat, because with such a low index score, the country, its stock market, and investment funds do not look attractive to investors. This factor is also seen as a threat to domestic investment funds, as there may be difficulties in starting and operating a fund. However, on the other hand, corruption makes it possible to establish contacts in the new market more quickly.

Next, let's take a closer look at economic factors. Economic factors include global economic crises, GDP, inflation, ease of doing business index, competitiveness of the economy, and the level of openness of the economy, which must be evaluated when analyzing the macro environment. Examples of economic factors include:

- according to the latest OECD economic forecast, the global economy will remain resilient despite significant challenges. According to the forecast, global GDP growth will be 3.3% in 2025, compared to 3.2% in 2024 and 3.3% in 2026. The forecast emphasizes ongoing uncertainty. Intensifying conflicts in the Middle East could disrupt energy markets and negatively impact confidence and economic growth. Rising trade ten-

sions could hamper trade growth. Unfavorable surprises related to growth prospects or through disinflation could cause disruptive corrections in financial markets. Growth can also be unexpected on the positive side. Improved consumer sentiment, for example, if purchasing power recovers faster than expected, could spur spending. A speedy resolution of major geopolitical conflicts could also improve sentiment and lower energy prices. To overcome these challenges, the Outlook emphasizes the need to sustainably reduce inflation, address rising fiscal pressures, and address labor shortages to mitigate structural impediments to higher growth [15]. On the one hand, this may lead to more people favoring classic savings over investment. On the other hand, another part of the population will invest in securities, especially bonds, in order to minimize the effects of inflation, possible devaluation of the national currency, and capital growth. Therefore, this factor should be viewed as both an opportunity and a threat to the activities of Ukrainian investment funds;

- reduction of economic and financial assistance to Ukraine from international partners in 2025. The National Bank of Ukraine expects a significant reduction in financial assistance to Ukraine from international partners in 2025-2026. The NBU's baseline forecast for 2024 envisages USD 37.4 billion of financial assistance from partners. The NBU's baseline forecast for 2014 envisages receiving USD 37.4 billion in financial assistance from partners. In 2025, this amount will be reduced to 25.1 billion, and in 2026 to 12.6 billion dollars [16]. If hostilities continue or even intensify, a reduction in external financial assistance will pose risks to the sustainability of public finances and the economy as a whole. Accordingly, this, in turn, will affect the general welfare of the population, the activities of investment funds in Ukraine, and the functioning of the domestic stock market;

- GDP growth. According to the Ministry of Economy, in June 2024, Ukraine's GDP grew by 1.1% compared to June last year. As a result, for the first half of the year, GDP growth is estimated at 4.1% compared to the same period last year [17]. According to the updated government forecast, real GDP growth is expected to reach 3.5% in 2024 [18]. Of course, it should be understood that the overall economic condition and welfare of the Ukrainian population cannot grow at a record pace during a full-scale war, but in any case, the very fact that GDP is growing at 3-4% is a positive signal and gives hope for real growth of the Ukrainian economy, which will ultimately increase investment attractiveness, intensify the stock market;

- starting from December 1, 2024, taxes in Ukraine will increase. The main change is an increase in the military tax on the salaries of all individuals from 1.5% to 5%, and from January 1, 2025, the income tax for non-banking institutions (except insurance companies) will increase from 18% to 25% [19]. It is obvious that such changes will in no way contribute to the general welfare of the population, but rather worsen the welfare of the population and further increase the shadow economy. On the other hand, military bonds will become more attractive to investors, as they are not

subject to taxation, compared to other financial assets and bank deposits;

- according to the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine, the inflation rate in 2021 was 10%, and in 2022, 2023 and as of November 2024 - 26.6%, 5.1% and 10.4%, respectively [20]. The NBU expects that in 2025 the inflation rate will begin to decline and will drop to 6.9% by the end of the year [21]. However, the real picture is that the inflation rate, as well as the overall economy of Ukraine, will depend on the situation on the battlefield, the intensity of hostilities, territorial losses, etc. A decrease in external financial assistance will also have a negative impact. However, on the other hand, in order to avoid the effects of inflation, the population may increase demand for the services of investment funds or for the direct purchase of certain financial assets, including government bonds;

- the devaluation of the national currency has been observed in Ukraine in recent years. The key driver of this is the ongoing war in Ukraine, as well as the prospects for a reduction in external financial assistance, especially from the United States. Thus, as of February 22, 2022, the dollar to hryvnia exchange rate was UAH 29.05 per USD 1. On the same date in 2023, it was 40.28 UAH, and on December 17, 2024, it was 41.97 UAH [22]. Unfortunately, it is expected that the Ukrainian hryvnia will continue to devalue in 2025. Thus, the Ukrainian government has set the dollar exchange rate at 45 UAH in the draft budget for 2025 [23]. However, this forecast is not 100% correct, as, for example, the budget for 2023 included an average forecast exchange rate of 42.2 UAH per 1 USD. Although the average exchange rate was almost 3 hryvnias less in 2023. However, it should not be forgotten that external financial assistance to Ukraine is expected to decrease in 2025, so there is every chance that the real dollar to hryvnia exchange rate in 2025 will be even higher than budgeted. The fact of further devaluation of the Ukrainian national currency may contribute to the growth of investments by individuals and the corporate sector in foreign currency, securities, and government securities, as they are not subject to taxation.

Social factors include population size, emigration and immigration rates, urbanization, preferences in certain areas, etc. All of these factors play an important role in shaping consumer preferences and also have a significant impact on the activities of investment funds. Social factors that have an impact on the environment of investment funds in Ukraine include the following:

- changes in investment preferences of the population: the growing popularity of conservative instruments, such as bond funds, due to low risk. According to UAIB, as of December 2024, the share of bond funds is gradually increasing - from 9% in 2019 to 13% in 2024 [1];

- according to the Institute of Demography and Social Studies of the National Academy of Sciences, the population of Ukraine was 42 million people as of January 1, 2022, and 35.8 million people as of July 2024, including 31.1 million people in the territories where public authorities exercise their powers in full [24]. This factor should be considered a threat, as the

potential number of clients of investment funds is decreasing;

- after the outbreak of Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine, many people, mostly women and children, were forced to emigrate abroad. Thus, according to the UN, as of December 16, 2024, the number of Ukrainians abroad was almost 6.8 million [25]. For Ukraine, whose population before the war amounted to almost 42 million people, this figure is significant, as it accounts for almost 20% of the total population. Therefore, this factor should also be considered as a threat, as the potential number of clients of investment funds is decreasing;

- according to various sources, approximately 22-24% of the territory of Ukraine is currently occupied by Russian invading forces. This factor should be viewed as a threat, as the potential number of clients of Ukrainian investment funds is being forcibly reduced. In addition, entire enterprises or part of the assets of companies whose shares are currently held by some Ukrainian investment funds remain in the occupied territories;

- the level of financial literacy in Ukraine is low. According to the OECD methodology, the overall financial literacy index of Ukraine in 2021 was 12.3 points (or 58% of its maximum value of 21 points) [26]. Unfortunately, more up-to-date data is not available, but it is unlikely that the Covid-19 pandemic and the full-scale war in Ukraine have significantly contributed to improving financial literacy. However, on a positive note, this year the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine approved the National Strategy for the Development of Financial Literacy until 2030 [27]. This strategy will help to improve financial literacy of the Ukrainian population, which in turn will affect the increase in investments, as more and more people will understand the benefits of this;

- according to the UNDP, as of March 2024, Ukraine's Human Development Index (HDI) is 0.734, making it a country with a high level of human development. Ukraine ranks 100th in the overall ranking of 193 countries and territories. At the same time, the negative impact of the decline in human development is acutely felt in Ukraine, as this indicator has fallen to its lowest level since 2004. Between 1990 and 2022, Ukraine's HDI increased from 0.731 to 0.734, i.e. by 0.4% [28]. From this we can conclude that, according to the HDI, such components as a long and healthy life, access to knowledge, and a decent standard of living have hardly improved in Ukraine over the past 20 years. Accordingly, this factor does not contribute to the development of financial literacy, which in turn could contribute to the development of the investment market.

Technological factors of the macro environment play an important role in the modern business environment. These factors are associated with the development and implementation of new products and technologies. This, in turn, can cause the emergence of a new industry or the liquidation of an existing industry. Technological factors are presented in more detail below:

- digitalization of financial services: financial services are increasingly developing and digitalizing in

Ukraine every year. For example, before the start of the full-scale war, in January 2022, Ukraine experienced a boom in smartphone investment applications [29]. Another example is that today almost all Ukrainians have access to purchasing government bonds through banking websites or mobile applications, or through the Diya portal [30]. The development of these initiatives contributes to the popularization of portfolio investment among Ukrainians, making this process as simple as possible;

- according to the State Statistics Service, by 2023 the share of research and development expenditures in relation to GDP decreased to 0.33%. For comparison, in 2019 the share was 0.43% with a higher GDP level [31]. Unfortunately, this fact is the reality of the current situation in Ukraine - a country against which a full-scale war is being waged. Spending on Ukraine's defense capability is currently a more important and priority area. Therefore, this fact does not contribute to the development of the investment market, the emergence of new investment funds etc.;

- the development of financial technologies and big data in Ukraine: every year more and more new technological solutions appear in Ukraine to attract investors. Examples, as noted above, are the same portal Diya, mobile applications of leading Ukrainian banks and investment companies. In addition, big data technology and its analytical tools are increasingly used by investment funds to optimize portfolio management and funds in general. This factor contributes to the development of the investment market as a whole, as well as to the more effective functioning of investment funds.

Environmental factors in the study of the macro environment of investment funds in the Ukrainian market do not play a decisive role, but they are still worth noting, especially in the context of a sustainable international portfolio investment strategy. Below are examples of several environmental factors that affect the functioning of investment funds in Ukraine:

- the emergence of regulation in the field of sustainable investment and financing. Thus, in November 2021, the National Bank presented the Policy on the Development of Sustainable Financing for the Period Until 2025. The document, developed in cooperation with the International Finance Corporation (IFC), is aimed at shaping the future landscape of sustainable financing and investment in Ukraine [32]. Initiatives of this type have a positive impact on increasing the efficiency of the functioning of investment funds in Ukraine, helping them adapt to modern requirements, as well as the requirements of the EU on Ukraine's path to full integration;

- negative environmental consequences for Ukraine caused by the war. According to the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources of Ukraine, since the beginning of the full-scale Russian invasion, at least 5,531 cases of negative environmental impacts have been registered, with losses estimated at 2.562 trillion hryvnias. [33] This factor does not directly affect the activities of investment funds in Ukraine, but it emphasizes the importance of creating

appropriate sustainable products or generally sustainable investment funds to help overcome catastrophic negative environmental consequences.

The final group of macro-environmental factors are legal factors, which mainly include regulatory and legislative changes affecting the activities of investment funds. Some of these factors are presented below:

- unification with EU norms. On June 25, 2024, Ukraine and the EU officially began negotiations [34]. In accordance with this stage of Ukraine-EU relations, Ukraine is currently undergoing a gradual adaptation of its legislation to EU legislation within the framework of the negotiation chapters. Adaptation and unification processes will also affect the activities of investment funds, because, for example, today CII in Ukraine are regulated by national legislation, in particular the Law of Ukraine "On Collective Investment Institutions" and the regulations of the National Securities and Markets Commission, while the regulation of investment funds in the EU is carried out on the basis of Directives such as UCITS (Undertakings for Collective Investment in Transferable Securities) and AIFMD (Alternative Investment Fund Managers Directive) [35, 36];

- according to the rule of law index, Ukraine ranks 88th out of 142 countries in this ranking according to data for 2024 (72nd place in 2019) [37]. With an overall index of 0.49/1, Ukraine still lags behind the world average of 0.56. This factor should be considered as a threat, since Ukraine's index is still not at a high level and therefore will not contribute to attracting additional investments into the Ukrainian economy;

- a ban on cross-border currency transfers from Ukraine. As a general rule, from 24.02.2022, authorized institutions are prohibited from carrying out cross-border transfers of currency values from Ukraine/transfers of funds to correspondent accounts of non-resident banks in hryvnia/foreign currency opened in resident banks, including transfers made on behalf of clients [38]. This factor negatively affects the activities of Ukrainian investment funds, since according to this ban they cannot purchase foreign securities and include them in their investment portfolios.

Summing up the analysis of the factors of the macro environment of investment funds in Ukraine, it is worth noting that most of the above PESTEL factors and sub-factors have a more negative impact on the functioning and conduct of investment funds than a positive one, in particular, the key obstacle is the continuation of the full-scale war. However, there are also a number of positive factors that, as the war ends and Ukraine's further comprehensive recovery and accession to the EU, will contribute to increasing the efficiency of investment funds and the stock market as a whole.

The next thing to focus on is the micro-environmental factors, namely competitors, suppliers, intermediaries and consumers. According to the authors, the factor of contact audiences does not have a significant impact on the activities of investment funds in the Ukrainian market, therefore their assessment is not carried out.

Table 3

Factors of micro-environment of investment funds in the Ukrainian market	
Group of factors	Factors
Consumers	- Low level of financial literacy of the population
Suppliers	- Reduction in the number of asset management companies on the market
Intermediaries	- Growing role of digital platforms
Competitors	- Introduction of the possibility of purchasing securities through mobile applications
	- Increasing number of competitors in the market
	- Fewer market alternatives

Source: compiled by the author according to [1, 26-28, 38].

Consumers in the investment market are directly the clients of investment funds. Factors related to consumers include the following:

- the level of financial literacy in Ukraine is low. According to the OECD methodology, the overall financial literacy index of Ukraine in 2021 was 12.3 points (or 58% of its maximum value – 21 points) [26]. Unfortunately, there are no more current data, but it is unlikely that the Covid-19 pandemic and the full-scale war in Ukraine have significantly contributed to increasing the financial literacy of the population. However, among the positive aspects is the fact that this year the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine approved the National Strategy for the Development of Financial Literacy until 2030 [27]. That is, thanks to educational programs and relevant strategies, the situation is gradually improving.

Asset management companies can be included among the suppliers in the investment fund market,

since in most cases they are the ones who manage investment funds. The following are among the supplier factors:

- reduction in the number of asset management companies (AMCs) in Ukraine. According to the UAIB, the number of asset management companies in Ukraine has been gradually decreasing since 2021 [1]. This is primarily due to the prolonged war in Ukraine and new regulatory challenges. In addition, there is some consolidation in the AMC market in Ukraine - the trend towards a reduction in the number of AMCs is also explained by increased requirements for efficiency and financial stability. Market consolidation contributes to the fact that fewer AMCs manage a larger number of investment funds, ensuring cost optimization and improved service quality.

The next group of microenvironment factors are intermediaries. In the investment fund market, intermediaries include banks, brokers, and platforms for purchasing securities. The following are intermediary factors:

- the growth of the role of digital platforms for purchasing securities in Ukraine. Thus, according to the Minister of Digital Transformation Fedorov M., in a day Ukrainians bought military bonds worth over 30 million UAH through "Diya" [38]. Using the example of military bonds, one can see how simple and fast the process of purchasing securities can be for both individual and professional investors;

- the introduction of the possibility of purchasing securities via mobile applications. For example, before the start of a full-scale war, in January 2022, Ukraine saw a boom in smartphone investment applications [28]. However, due to the start of a full-scale Russian war against Ukraine, which still prohibits cross-border transfers of currency from Ukraine, the functionality of such applications is quite limited - only the purchase of military bonds in hryvnia and foreign currency is possible. However, this also facilitates the process of purchasing securities for both individual and professional investors.

One of the key groups of factors in the framework of the study of the microenvironment of investment funds in Ukraine is the analysis of competitors. This group of factors includes both competition purely in the investment funds market and competition from the point of view of available alternatives to investment funds. The competitor factors are described in more detail below:

- according to the Ukrainian Association of Investment Business (UAIB), as of December 2024, 1828 recognized collective investment institutions were registered in Ukraine [1]. Compared to 2019, the "pre-crisis" year, the number of investment funds has increased by almost 35%. This indicates that there are more and more players on the Ukrainian market, which from the point of view of a particular investment fund is considered a threat. However, the annual growth in the number of investment funds in Ukraine is due to the creation of new venture corporate investment funds and mutual funds, and as noted earlier, these types of funds are created not for the implementation of classical portfolio investment activities, but to optimize taxation by individual business entities or for their restructuring. It is also worth noting that the interest of foreign funds in the Ukrainian market is still limited due to political risks and the instability of the regulatory environment;

- in Ukraine, the main alternatives to investing in investment funds are pension funds, bank deposits, purchasing real estate or building individual investment portfolios. Compared to the markets of developed European countries, there are currently a small number of

market alternatives in Ukraine, because, first of all, there is a ban on cross-border transfer of currency values from Ukraine. That is, investors do not have the opportunity to purchase foreign securities. Returning to alternatives to investment funds, it is worth noting why these entities and individual investment objects are alternatives for investment funds. Pension funds: they are long-term accumulation instruments, similar in structure and asset management principles to investment funds. They are focused on ensuring financial stability in the future, attractive to those who seek stability and lower risks. Bank deposits: deposits are traditionally associated with low risks and guaranteed returns, which competes with the conservative strategies of investment funds. Real estate acquisition: investments in real estate are considered a protected asset, especially in conditions of economic instability. This is an alternative focused on long-term preservation of asset value. Individual investment portfolios: provide the opportunity for personalized capital management, which is attractive to experienced investors. In fact, this is a competitive alternative for those who are ready to independently analyze the market and make decisions.

Investment funds are the best option for those who seek to combine risk diversification with professional asset management. At the same time, for conservative investors, alternatives such as bank deposits or real estate may remain attractive due to the low level of risk. The advantages of funds compared to other alternatives are especially clearly manifested in the context of increasing financial literacy and stabilizing the economic situation.

Thus, the micromarketing environment of investment funds in Ukraine is characterized by pressure due to competition between funds, as well as due to the low level of financial literacy of the population. At the same time, prospects for growth are opening up due to the increasing role of digital platforms, the introduction of the possibility of purchasing securities through mobile applications, and the presence of a small number of market alternatives during the war.

The final stage of conducting a factor analysis of the business environment of investment funds in Ukraine is the construction of a SWOT analysis. It is worth noting that macro factors create threats and opportunities for investment funds, which the funds themselves can hardly influence. Micro factors shape the strengths and weaknesses of investment funds, which the investment funds themselves can influence (Table 4).

Table 4

SWOT analysis of the business environment of investment funds in Ukraine	
<p>Strengths (S)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Growing role of digital platforms; - Introduction of the possibility of purchasing CPUs through mobile applications; - Small number of market alternatives 	<p>Weaknesses (W)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction in the number of AMC's on the market; - Increase in the number of competitors on the market
<p>Opportunities (O)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deepening integration with the EU; - Sustainability of the global economy despite uncertainty; - Digitalization of financial and investment services; - Development of financial technologies and big data; - Emergence of regulation in the field of sustainable investment and financing in Ukraine; - Gradual unification with EU norms 	<p>Threats (T)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full-scale russian war against Ukraine; - Low level of political stability; - High level of corruption; - Reduction of economic and financial assistance from international partners - Rising inflation rate; - Devaluation of the national currency; - Reduction of population due to external migration, occupation of part of the territory of Ukraine and as a result of military actions; - Low level of financial literacy of the population; - Low level of the rule of law index; - Low level of the human development index; - Significant scale of negative environmental and social consequences caused by the war; - Effect of the ban on cross-border currency transfers from Ukraine

Source: author's development

Conclusion

Thus, investment funds in Ukraine have significant potential for development due to the growing role of digital platforms and the introduction of opportunities to purchase securities through mobile applications or websites, and due to the limited number of market alternatives during martial law. At the same time, their growth is constrained by weaknesses, such as an increase in the number of competitors on the market while reducing the number of suppliers in the form of asset management companies. The main opportunities for the development of investment funds in Ukraine lie in the gradual unification with EU norms, the digitalization of financial and investment services, and the emergence of regulation in the field of sustainable investment and financing in Ukraine. The threats in the form of a continuation of a full-scale war in Ukraine and the negative economic, environmental, social and technological consequences caused by it are complemented by Ukraine's low performance in economic, political and technological indices, as well as the low level of financial literacy of the population.

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